

Design and Implementation of Emergency Hospital Wireless Call Device and its Benefits (A Case Study of KSITM Clinic)

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ABSTRACT

The hospital wireless caller device is a tool used in healthcare facilities, such as hospital or nursing homes, to quickly summon medical assistance in case of an emergency. It is used as a special communication device between the patients and the doctor or nurse within the area as a means of speeding the doctor or nurse's time response in providing immediate care to the patients. The device typically consists of a button or switch that can be easily pressed by patients or staff in need of assistant. The use of hospital wireless-based caller device makes communication easier and neater between the two parties. The Bluetooth module MH-10 is connected to the microcontroller ATMega8 as the sender and receiver. The information is processed using a microcontroller ATMega8 that produces characters on the LCD, turns on the LED, and activates the buzzer to call the doctor or nurse.

Keywords: Hospital, Nurse Caller, Arduino microcontroller.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The hospital is an essential part of a social and health organization with the function of providing plenary (comprehensive), healing (curative), and disease prevention (preventive) services to the community, whose services are handled by nurses, doctors, and other health experts. The nurses are considered the spearhead in the organization of hospital services because it is the nurse who continually provides care to the patients. The nurse continues to monitor the patient's health and provide care to them. Numerous previous studies have conducted research on nurse callers. The techno-economic evaluation of an ontology-based nurse call system through discrete event simulations was investigated by (Vannieuwenborg, 2014). The design and implementation of the Wired Nurse Call System was researched by (C. Sharma, 2015). A study on the automatic evaluation method of designating and invoking nurse education was researched by (al., 2015). (N. Khera, 2016) researched the development of smart house call systems and android-based nurses for different abilities.

A real time feedback-centric nurse call system with archival monitoring using a Raspberry Pi was studied by (M. S. Mahmud, 2017). The hospital is equipped with a calling device in each patient's bedroom to speed up patient services. Presently, the nurse calling device used is very conventional, namely, it still uses a pair of cables. Electronic technology innovation is one way for patients and nurses to interact more quickly. A component that can calculate, remember, and make choices using a microcontroller is needed to make this device. The microcontroller is a chip or an integrated circuit (IC) that contains a processor and a flash memory capable of reading and writing up to 1000 times. The cost of development is inexpensive because it can be minimized and refilled with other programs as needed. This nurse caller uses wireless technology so that the installation does not require a lot of cables.

1.1 Problem Statement

The project idea is to develop an emergency wireless call system for patients and nurses that enables patients to initiate an emergency call to their nurse and provides nurses with access to patient information and location tracking. The system aims to streamline the medical assistance process, reduce delays in diagnosis and treatment, and ultimately improve patient outcomes. The system will provide doctors with access to patient information such as medical history, allergies, and current medications, which can be crucial for making informed decisions during an emergency call. Additionally, the system can track the patient's location/bed to enable doctors to provide quick response based on the patient's location. In summary, the proposed hospital wireless call system for patients and doctors is a unique and innovative solution that aims to initiate an emergency call to their doctor and providing doctors with access to patient information and location tracking, the system is designed to be compliant with relevant security and privacy regulations, ensuring that patient data is protected and confidential.

1.2 Objectives Of The Study

The aim of the Research is to develop a hospital emergency wireless call system for patients and doctors to improve emergency medical assistance. This is to be realized by achieving the following objectives:

- a. To enable patients to initiate emergency calls to their doctors.
- b. To provide doctors with patient information and location tracking.
- c. To streamline the medical assistance process and reduce delays in diagnosis and treatment.
- d. To improve patient outcomes by providing timely and personalized medical assistance.
- e. To ensure compliance with relevant security and privacy regulations.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Wireless network technology has been widely researched by previous researchers. The WI-FI Microcontroller-based Capacitive Water Wireless Sensor System Model was studied by (S. Suryono, 2018). (Bhagat, 2018) Obtaining Information About Neighbouring Street Lights Using the WIFI Mesh Network was researched by (C. S.N., 2018). (Martinez, 2017) investigated Wi-Fi Activated Speech Recognition Control Nodes. (Z. Xiao, 2018) investigated the design of Wi-Fi internet of things (IoT)-based household appliance control systems for Smart Homes. An efficient remote control system using SMS and Wi-Fi technology for outdoor security lighting applications was studied by (M. F. Akorede, 2017). (Wang, 2017) investigated a smart car design based on Wi-Fi video capture and Open CV motion control. A 220-volt power switch controlled through Wi-Fi was studied by (X. Gao, 2016).

The Internet- based monitoring and protection of the smart PV grid system was studied by (S. H. Pramono, 2018). A real-time carbon dioxide emission system based on participatory sensing technology based on (R. Yu, 2011). (W. Tian-He, 2018) investigated Comprehensive Monitoring and Analysis Instrument Design for Mine Environment. Smart Community Monitoring Platform for Smart Homes that Actually Work was researched by (Subodh, 2018). The equipment control and environmental environment of the smart home were investigated by (Z. Shiqi, 2018). An Automated Service Request System for Security in Smart Homes Using the Internet of Things (IoT) was investigated by (Karthikeyan, 2018).The Monitoring and Ventilation Control System for Multi-story Historic Buildings

was studied by (A. Singh, 2017). Nurse calling devices can facilitate communication between patients and nurses in the hospital area when patients need aid in an emergency.

Since we are aiming to develop a hospital emergency wireless call system for patients and doctors to improve emergency medical assistance. This can significantly improve the response time to medical emergencies, as patients can quickly and easily connect with their doctors through the emergency call system and can lead to faster diagnosis and treatment. This nurse calling device is different from the nurse caller that has been researched by previous researchers.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Implementation strategy: The implantation processes of the system are as follows, Panning, Analysis, Design and Development, Testing, Implementation, evaluation and feedback and scaling up the emergency call system between patients and doctors:

Project Planning: The first step in the project development process is to create a comprehensive project plan. This plan should include the project goals, objectives, timeline, budget, and resources required. It should also outline the roles and responsibilities of the project team members, including developers, designers, healthcare professionals, and legal experts.

Research and Analysis: The next step is to conduct research and analysis to identify the needs and requirements of patients and doctors. This can involve surveys, interviews, and focus groups to gather feedback and insights. It is important to ensure that the software meets the needs of users and is integrated into existing healthcare systems.

Design and Development: Once the research and analysis phase is complete, the design and development phase can begin. This phase involves creating the user interface and user experience (UI/UX) design, developing the software, and integrating it with existing systems. It is important to ensure that the software is user-friendly, accessible, and secure. The development process should follow best practices for software development, including agile methodologies, version control, and automated testing.

Testing and Quality Assurance: After the software has been developed, it should be thoroughly tested to ensure that it meets the project requirements and is free from bugs and errors. Quality assurance measures should be put in place to ensure that the software is reliable and performs as expected. This can involve automated testing, manual testing, and user acceptance testing (UAT).

Implementation: Once the software has been tested and approved, it can be implemented. This involves deploying the software in a controlled environment and monitoring its performance. It is important to ensure that the software is integrated with existing systems and that users are trained on how to use it. The implementation process should follow best practices for software deployment, including change management, backup and recovery, and disaster recovery.

Evaluation and Feedback: After the software has been implemented, it is important to evaluate its performance and gather feedback from users. This feedback can be used to make improvements and ensure that the software meets the needs of patients and doctors. The evaluation process should follow best practices for software evaluation, including metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs), user feedback, and continuous improvement.

Scaling Up: Once the software has been successfully implemented and evaluated, it can be scaled up. This involves expanding the use of the software to more patients and doctors, and potentially integrating it with other healthcare systems. The scaling up process should follow best practices for software scaling, including load testing, capacity planning, and performance optimization. **Maintenance and Support:** After the software has been scaled up, it is important to provide ongoing maintenance and support. This involves fixing bugs, making improvements, and providing technical support to users. The maintenance and support process should follow best practices for software maintenance, including incident management, problem management, and change management.

To ensure the success of the project, it is important to involve all stakeholders, including patients, doctors, and healthcare providers, in the development and implementation process. This can help to ensure that the software meets the needs of users and is integrated into existing healthcare systems.

4.0 THE BENEFITS OF ADOPTING A WIRELESS NURSE CALL SYSTEM

1. Instant communication and quicker response time The wireless nurse call systems give patients access to timely care, especially in terrible situations where response time decides the odds in the battle of life and death. The wireless nurse call system alerts the medical staff and sends them the exact location of the patient that requires or needs medical attention. If the patient is wearing a wireless hand transmitter, then she or he can be found anywhere inside the care facility or hospital. an advanced mobile application for smartphones, which enables them to be informed and react even when they are not in the vicinity of the nurse's station. The Nurse mobile application is an advanced replacement for pagers or DECT phones. How so? Because it also enables nurses to see which personnel are currently working and allows them to make direct assistance calls without using a SIM card.

2. Relieving the personnel Many hospitals still rely on paper documentation, which delays the process of patient admission, medical research, and diagnosis. Nevertheless, healthcare management can be optimized. With an intelligent wireless nurse call system, you can digitalize your healthcare administration and save all information inside a cloud database connected to the hospital network. That is not all! An IP nurse call system like Nurse Care allows medical personnel to store and access patient information instantly. The Nurse Tab, an interactive room touchscreen display, and the interactive corridor display Info Tab connect the nurse call system, the entire healthcare management system, and nursing documentation into one device. Nurses can store patient information and updates from inside a patient's room or the hallway. The latter eradicates the need to fill out documents, and it likewise prevents the loss of data or repetition of information. In most cases, this happens when the nurses transcribe handwritten data into electronic form.

3. Better workflow and fewer disturbances Enhanced workflow cuts down on any potential losses, both in time, money, and knowledge. With an intelligent nurse call system, every piece of data is stored instantly, accessible with a simple touch, and transmitted among medical staff. Better communication leads to better decisions and better organization. It likewise helps lower the number of medical errors, which affects not only the hospital's budget but also its reputation. With nurse care, there are fewer disturbances in the healthcare process since it provides prompt and timely patient care. It helps nurses stay organized and keeps them focused on dealing with patient care, not distractions.

4. Fewer mistakes and cost-effectiveness Monitoring technology benefits both the medical staff and the hospital management. Healthcare workers treat several patients throughout the day. In this process, data gets handed down many times, resulting in loss of data or even a medical error. With monitoring technology, such as Nurse Tab, healthcare processes are under constant supervision, guaranteeing patient safety. The Nurse Tab enables medical personnel to log (a) The personnel assigned to work in a specific patient room, (b) The time they will arrive and the time allotted (c). Nursing notes, (d) Services provided, (e) the patient's name in care.

When you consider the long-term benefits and the initial cost, you realize that employing a wireless nurse call system pays off. Especially when you can connect it to your existing nurse call system and use the installation that is already in the building. You can personalize and select only those features that will benefit you the most.

5. Satisfied staff, satisfied patients Satisfactory, attentive, and efficient patient care results in pleased and comfortable patients, who are likely to recover quicker. Wireless nurse call systems quicken the treatment processes, optimize workflow, and decrease the level of stress in hospitals and other caring facilities. These intelligent solutions are easy to use, which helps keep hospital tasks moving smoothly and efficiently.

5.0 CONCLUSION

After the process of making, experimenting, testing, and data collection, the author can conclude that making a nurse call device using a Bluetooth module can simplify installation and will look neat. To make these devices, we needed a component that could calculate, remember, and take choices using a microcontroller. Displaying the commands found on the LCD and LED will make it easier for nurses to get information on the patient's room that is calling. Based on the results of taking information on measurements outside the room, horizontally and vertically, we prove that the wind can affect the frequency of the Bluetooth module so that the distance measurements get different results. The impact of installing the wireless nurse calling system is discussed.

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